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CHESSET UP

Deliverable 5.3 CONSTRUCTION CONCLUSIONS REPORT

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1. Introduction

Not everything that can be counted counts and not everything that counts can be counted.

This report shows a summary of the main construction activity carried out in the three pilots of the CHESSE SETUP project. For the three cases, it shows a timeline with scheduled versus accomplished tasks and the percentage of development during the construction phase and a description of the main conclusions for each pilot. The information is accompanied by a photo report where it is possible to see the evolution of each of the three pilots

A quick guide with the main parameters to take into consideration for the CHESSE SETUP implementation is also incorporated.

Executive Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lavola, Grup Soler and Wattia prepare the executive project for the Eco building in Manlleu during November 2017-January 2018.
Council permits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> On the 23rd of March 2018, the City Council issued the licences for the works in Lavola's pilot.
PV installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The photovoltaic installation works start date was shifted from March to June 2018, as shown in the calendar. On the 27th April 2018, the contract with the photovoltaic supplier was signed. The works started on the 4th of June with the replacement of the roof cantilever to identify the structural pillars of the building and check the status of the water insulation layer. There were adverse weather conditions during the first week of works, with heavy rains almost every day that slowed down the works on the roof. The replacement of the current solar trackers, electrical and control wires works were carried out (5th-20th July 2018). The assemblage of the new metallic structure and the installation of solar photovoltaic panels were done at the end of August due to delays from the supplier.
HP installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Preparation of the hydraulic installation and building the concrete slab for the new heat pump during June-July 2018. From to June to November, Lavola and CST Ulster University worked together to determine which of the commercial heat pumps was the most suitable for the pilot, which was ordered to Carrier after financial approval from the CHESS SETUP project in March 2019. At the end of March 2019, Carrier did not have heat pumps available in stock, having to be manufactured with a delivery period of 6 weeks. The reception and installation of the heat pump were on the 15th of May 2019.
Commissioning and start-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The heat pump commissioning was carried out on the 2nd of July 2019 after installing the metering elements (temperature sensors, heat meter, electric meter), still pending the integration of the meters to the control software. The control system software integration was carried out during August-September 2019. <p><u>Ongoing maintenance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> It was noticed that the first floor was over cooled. During the week starting on 15th July 2019, it was found that a piece of weld spatter remained in the circuit and blocked the valve. The maintenance service reviewed the system to detect it and disassemble the valve to remove the waste that avoided that valve could close 100%. The 23rd of July 2019, the heat pump stopped because of lack of pressure. It could have happened because of the tasks of the first-floor valve problem. The heat pump has stopped 3 times since it was commissioned. This issue was reported to Carrier and sorted in the period August-September 2019. During the colder months of December and January, the heat pump suffered successive defrosting operations. This fact limited to arrive at the setpoint temperature established. The problem was notified to Carrier. The first solution was to increase the setpoint temperature of the buffer tank until Carrier could analyze the problem adequately. It is still pending the second visit of the Carrier technician to follow up the defrosting. However, February has not been such cold, and the heat pump worked adequately.
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data collection from the CHESS SETUP system was planned to start in June 2019 to obtain data for a full year. As the photovoltaic panels were installed before the full CHESS SETUP installation, data from the electricity generation has been obtained since September 2018 with full CHESS SETUP monitoring data recorded since 30th August 2019 (except for the thermal meter that data was available since 15th October 2019).

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Executive Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Electric Corby presented the project by Glendale Ecohomes Ltd (now known as Etopia Corby Ltd).
Council permits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Planning consent achieved for Corby's pilot in December 2016.
Site preparation works	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Despite the project achieved planning consent in December 2016, there was a change in ownership of the entire Corby development (around 5,500 homes) which has meant that the construction of the pilot did not start as planned. Note: This delay meant that the block of apartments would not be available before the end of the project. (a.) Site preparation was carried out in May-September 2018 with completion of the access roadway for the construction compound and grading of the site in readiness for the construction of the first 4 homes. (b.) Site grading and clearance for the next 6 homes have been undertaken, and foundations will start in January 2019. Site groundworks is a rolling program working around the site and on-going beyond those homes that are part of CHESS-SETUP.
Earth Energy Bank (EEB)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (a.) Construction has progressed through October-November 2018 with the foundations and EEB's for the first 4 houses complete along with the drainage and rear road access construction in progress. (b.) Construction of remaining EEB's has progress reasonably well only delayed by poor weather and therefore ground conditions. 22 EEBs are now installed
Homes construction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Following the initial delay, individual home construction progressed well but was again delayed for reasons set out in the Conclusions section of the report Currently, 5 of the 26 planned homes are not complete while the cost of the individual ZCS installations has increased beyond the original budget
HP and PV installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HP and PV-T installation have gone smoothly but are obviously tied to the homes construction program, and the delays set out above and elsewhere PV-T failures in some batches required replacements with some delay – around a 3% failure rate currently
Commissioning and start-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> HP commissioning has been impacted by lack of optic fibre to the home broadband, but temporary arrangements for 4G connections have mitigated this to a degree
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data collection from the CHESS SETUP system was planned to start in June 2019 to obtain data for a full year. Data collection started from first homes in July 2019 and has been increasing as new homes completed. But construction delays have had a negative impact on this.

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Executive Project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sant Cugat prepares the pilot project design together with the CHESSE SETUP project team and is agreed after many efforts to reduce the costs of the project to fit within the project budget.
Council permits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The project requires a public tendering process, which will take a considerable amount of time (approximately 5 months). Planning consent is achieved, and works are ready to start in June 2018.
Roof reinforcement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The incorporation of the PVT panels to the existing roof together with the new regulation in relation to the wooden structure obliged to perform an expensive reinforcement of the roof from June 2018 to November 2018. At the same time, drilling was carried out on the roof to be able to make anchors with the benches of the panels.
Thermal store installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The tank was redesigned in the construction phase, making it cylindrical rather than square because it was easier to assemble. Despite this ease of construction, the new design and its approval caused a delay in the unwanted work. During the excavation process to build the structural foundations of the STES (starting June 2018), an asbestos cement pipe was found on site. This delayed the excavation works since it was then done manually, without machinery, in order not to damage the localized pipe and to keep the place safe. Parallel to these activities, the store started to be manufactured externally. Once on-site, the assembly of the 2.8 m high and 1.5 m wide rings will be carried out by means of welding. Despite the existence of an asbestos pipe, by December 2018 the reinforcement of the pavement where the tank will be built was made through a set of piles and a concrete slab. At the end of January 2019, all the rings arrived at the site, and 75% of them were assembled. The completion of the store was delayed to the second half of March 2018. In the period February-March 2019, the storage tank was mounted, insulated and connected to the hydraulic system.
PVT panels installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> During the period when the roof was being reinforced (June-November 2018), drilling was carried out on the roof to be able to make anchors with the benches of the panels. In December 2018 the metal support structure of the panels was anchored to the roof. As a test, one bench and its respective set of panels were installed, with the rest to be installed in January 2019. The process to bring the structure, benches and panels to the roof has been carried out through a mobile crane placed on the street. In January 2019, all benches and panels were installed. The footbridge was 80% installed, with only the first footbridge with the safety railing for maintenance awaiting to be installed. Finalized and connected to the electrical and hydraulic systems in March 2019.
Hydraulic & electric installation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regarding the hydraulic system, the installation of the pumping groups, the valves and their collectors begun in the period June 2018 to November 2018. The elements of the installation are manufactured externally and assembled by welding on site. The exchanger was received on-site and the heat pump, and the inertia tank ordered from the manufacturers waiting for their reception. During the same period (June-November 2018), the electrical installation started with the wire trays installed between the control computer and the rooms where the sensor and control elements are located and between the electrical cabinet and the supply points. By November 2018, contact was initiated with the electrical supplier company for the legalization of the self-consumption installation. In January 2019, the connections to the hydraulic system and to the electrical installation were carried out, including the main hydraulic elements (valves, pumps and heat exchangers). By March 2019, all elements of the system were connected hydraulically, and the sealing tests of the pipes carried out with satisfactory results. All panels also connected electrically. In the period February-March 2019, the electrical scheme was approved by the electrical supplier company. All the hydraulic and electrical installation was finalised in June 2019.
Commissioning and start-up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The commissioning and system start-up was planned to be finished by February 2019 but has delayed to the end of August beginning of September 2019. <p><u>Ongoing maintenance</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> During September and October 2019, the monitoring system was revised as some data was not being extracted as expected. 3 PVT panels were not working and were replaced in November 2019.
Data collection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data collection from the CHESSE SETUP system was planned to start in March 2019 to obtain data for over a full year. Data is being collected from the operating CHESSE SETUP system since September 2019.

3. Photo report of the pilots' implementation

In the next section, a detailed photographic report was made showing the evolution of each of the pilots, from the beginning to the start-up of the facilities.

3.1. Lavola's pilot

Fig. 01 – Building's roof before the works

Fig. 02. Disassembly of the current PV system

Fig. 03 – Solar track retirement

Fig. 04 – Structure assemblage

Fig. 05 - Assembly of the support structure of the new installation

Fig. 06 – PV array installation

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Fig. 07 - Concrete foundation for the heat pump

Fig. 08 – Heat pump installation

Fig.09 – Air source heat pump and buffer tank installed

Fig.10 – Heat pump and the hydraulic installation of the buffer

Fig.11 – Control and hydraulic system

Fig.12 – Control board installation

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Fig. 13 & 14 – Different meters installed

Fig. 15, 16 & 17 - Sensors installation in different equipments.

Fig. 18 & 19 – Front and lateral view of the PV installation completed

3.2. Corby's pilot

Fig. 20 - Ground and foundations work.

Fig. 21 – Heat exchangers to be installed into the boreholes for the EEB.

Fig. 22 - Drilling of boreholes for the Earth Energy Bank (EEB)

Fig. 23 - Installation of the heat exchangers

Fig. 24 - Isolation of the Earth Energy Bank (EEB)

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Fig. 25 & 26 – Foundations and isolation of the Earth Energy Bank (EEB)

Fig. 27 & 28 – Foundations and isolation of the Earth Energy Bank (EEB)

Fig. 29 – Housings facades

Fig. 30 - Construction site.

Fig. 31 & 32 – Interior of dwellings under construction

Fig. 33 – Fluid distribution connectors.

Fig.34 – Ground source heat pump

Fig.35 – Control system and battery

Fig.36 – Aerial view of the first four dwellings

Fig. 37 - Rear view of the dwellings (Plots 44- 47).

Fig. 38 - Working progress in Plots 03-09.

Fig. 39 - Working progress in Plots 03-11.

Fig. 40 - Working progress in Plots 10-21.

3.3. Sant Cugat's pilot

Fig. 41 – Pavilion roof before the intervention

Fig. 42 – Pavilion roof after the intervention
(anchors for branches)

Fig. 43 – Reinforce of the wooden structure

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Fig. 44 – Panels structure installed

Fig. 45 – First panels installed

Fig. 46 – PV-T structure support.

Fig. 47 – PV-T mounted on the roof.

Fig. 48 – Safe rooftop walkway with a guardrail.

Fig. 49 – Safe rooftop walkway with a guardrail.

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Fig. 50 – Piling and drilling rig machine

Fig. 51 – Asbestos cement pipe

Fig. 52 – Asbestos cement pipe

Fig. 53 – Foundation of the seasonal thermal energy storage (STES)

Fig. 54 – Foundation of the STES

Fig. 55 – Concrete slab finished

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Fig. 56 – Extreme covers of the STES

Fig. 57 – Body part of the STES

Fig. 58 – Front view of the STES

Fig. 59 – Rear view of the STES

Fig. 60 – Installation of the insulation of the STES

Fig. 61 – Assembly on the enclosure for the STES

Fig.62 – Front view of the STES room

Fig. 63 – Rear view of the STES room.

Fig. 64 & 65 – Pump groups and collectors

Fig. 66 & 67 – Overall view of the hydraulic installation

Fig. 68 – Pipes and buffer tanks

Fig. 69 – Water pumps

Fig.70 – Front view of the tank room

Fig. 71 & 72 – Hydraulic installation

Fig. 73 & 74 – Control and electrical installation.

Fig. 75 & 76 – Control and electrical installation.

Fig. 77 – Access stair to the PV-T installation

Fig. 78 – Inverters of the PV installation and protections

4. Guide for the CHESSE SETUP success

4.1. Design and implementation

This section describes the most important considerations that need to be taken into account for an adequate CHESSE SETUP implementation in a project.

The diagram below illustrates the paths that may be taken in each case depending on the demand type and profile first and the roof space and storage availability as the key elements of the project's architecture.

- Demand type and Profile

The demand type is defined by building use, which will have different energy demands. The CHESSE SETUP system is especially suitable for those buildings that have high heating and hot water demands.

The energy demand profile is also very relevant as a high and relatively constant hot water demand (typically found in hotels, sports centres and hospitals) will take the most advantage of the CHESSE SETUP system. The system proposed will smooth out the daily and moderate seasonal fluctuations in demand efficiently.

In case of having low and seasonal heating and hot water demands, such as in offices or residential buildings, the suitability of the CHESSE SETUP system needs to be considered carefully. It will greatly depend on the thermal storage space available to be able to cope with the demand seasonality.

By having a heat pump as a thermal energy generator, the system is capable of generating cooling as well, so it can be considered as a global solution for the entire thermal demand. It has not been put on the synoptic table because it is not within the scope of the European Chess Setup project, so dynamic simulations have not been performed.

- **Roof space available**

The roof space availability is an essential element to consider for the CHESSE SETUP design and implementation as it is the renewable energy source of the proposed system. If there is not enough available roof space to cover a significant portion of the demand, the CHESSE SETUP system would not be suitable in this case. The roof space availability is something that needs to be checked in the preliminary calculations and which can be a limiting factor in existing buildings.

Another critical factor is the state of conservation of the roof, especially in the case of using PV-T modules. The PV-T modules are very heavy, so make sure that the roof is capable of withstanding overweight. Having to perform cover reinforcement actions makes the investment considerably more expensive, and reduces the profitability of the system.

The roof must allow the south-facing modules to be installed and at a correct inclination, so it must be free of obstacles that may produce shadows.

- **Thermal storage deposit**

The thermal store space availability is undoubtedly a key element in the CHESSE SETUP design. Together with the production of the solar panels, the storage size will determine if the system is capable of supplying energy efficiently for the different demand-type scenarios. The higher and more seasonal the demand is, the larger the storage deposit will need to be.

If there is very limited or minimal space for a thermal store, an air source heat pump coupled with photovoltaic panels may be the best solution for this particular case, which is a variation from the original CHESSE SETUP system. In this case, the energy generated by the photovoltaic modules is used to cover the consumption of the heat pump compressor, obtaining a high degree of energy efficiency of the system, although the concept of seasonal accumulation does not exist.

Another possibility to consider is to bury the accumulator underground. This case is very viable in newly constructed buildings since the accumulator can be left installed in the initial phase of earthworks. It is an efficient system since the ground itself acts as insulation, while not occupying the interior space of the building.

- **Heat Pump**

The selection of the heat pumps needs to be analyzed carefully to size it properly to the thermal demand of the building and needs to be able to work in the temperature ranges that are considered in the CHESSE SETUP scenario. These heat pumps with lower ΔT provide much higher efficiencies than the industry average.

In case of having enough space for a seasonal storage system (heated with PV-T modules), the best option is undoubtedly the use of a water source heat pump, which ensures higher performance than air source heat pumps.

The efficiency of the system is based on heating the accumulator with the thermal energy generated by the solar panels, also covering the electrical consumption of the heat pump compressor with the electrical energy generated with the same panels. All this working at a very high COP thanks to the excellent performance of water-source heat pumps. These three

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elements (thermal generation, electricity generation and high-performance heat pump) combined correctly, can provide the system with energy self-sufficiency very close to 100%

- Solar energy panels

The solar energy panels proposed as part of the original CHESS SETUP system are hybrid solar thermal and photovoltaic panels. These produce electricity and hot water (at lower temperatures than traditional solar thermal panels) reducing the roof space required compared to installing them separately. Throughout these years, the market for hybrid solar panels has evolved and brought new models available depending on the technology they have been incorporating. The panels used in the Chess Setup project are the so-called second-generation hybrid panels. The main feature of these panels is the incorporation of a transparent front cover. With this, it is possible to alleviate what for some is the main drawback of the hybrid solar panels of previous generations: the loss of heat through the front face. Thus, insulating the panel itself on both sides achieves an even greater decrease in heat losses and, therefore, a considerable increase in the thermal efficiency of the panel. By reducing both heat losses, this panel is postulated as ideal for buildings with high demand, where the aim is to boost thermal production.

The installation of photovoltaic (PV) only may be considered for the cases where incorporating a thermal store is not possible, as a variation of the original CHESS SETUP system, as mentioned earlier.

5. Conclusions

Below is a compilation of conclusions of the construction process of each of the three pilots.

5.1. Lavola's pilot

The main conclusions of the Lavola's pilot constructions are:

- There was a significant delay in the implementation of the pilot. The commissioning and start-up phase of the installation was planned to end by October 2018, and finally finished by June 2019, and it was not working at full capacity until September 2019. The main reasons were:
 - Problems for the supply of the heat pump. Initially, the installation of a water-source heat pump was planned for this pilot. Due to space problems to locate the seasonal storage system and in accordance with the PO, was decided to change to an air-source heat pump when time and resources had already been invested in the construction of the first heat pump. Being a heat pump made to measure and very innovative, Ulster could not give a product warranty, which was not compatible with Lavola's requirements. Another reason that motivated the purchase of a heat pump from a conventional supplier was that Ulster needed a very high number of hours of operation in the laboratory to guarantee 100% correct operation of the equipment, which was not compatible with the time scale of the project. The delay caused by these events was about 8 months.
 - Extended commissioning of the installation. The commissioning of the installation was in June 2019, but during the first three months of operation, several problems arose that forced the old chiller to turn on many times. For this reason, the installation cannot be considered running 100% until September 2019. In this way, the total accumulated delay in the construction of the pilot was 11 months.
- The remaining phases (executive project, council permits and PV installation) of the project were executed according to the planned schedule.
- Data collection was planned to start in June 2019 to obtain data for a full year. As the photovoltaic panels were installed before the complete Chess Setup installation, data from the electricity generation has been obtained since September 2018.

5.2. Corby's pilot

The main conclusions of Corby's pilot constructions are:

- There was a significant initial delay to the start of the pilot construction due to the master developer Bela Partnership going into administration. This initial delay caused two main impacts:
 - an overall delay over more than one year and
 - The loss of the development funder.

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- Replacing the funder with Project Etopia altered the control structure for the project. Where previously Electric Corby CIC was a party to the development consortium, after Project Etopia stepped in to fund the pilot and enable progress, they took the day to day control of the main construction delivery
 - Those elements of the project within the control of Electric Corby CIC, such as permits, planning consent and supply of the ZCS services to the pilot site progressed on schedule
 - However, as a result of the initial delay, the pilot was scaled back to cover 26 instead of 31 homes based on a programme Project Etopia confirmed was deliverable
- Construction of the pilot accelerated in late 2018 through 2019 to achieve the revised schedule and timetable
 - Earth Energy Bank installation was implemented successfully on the first 10 homes quickly and, installation and commissioning of the PV-T and heat pumps likewise progressed well for these initial homes
- There were considerable challenges and delays when it comes to integrating the individually commissioned elements of the ZCS, and these were compounded by a delay in the utility company providing the fibre-to-home broadband. An interim arrangement had to be put in place in July 2019 using 4G routers and SIMs to ensure data could flow both to operate and monitor the heat pumps properly and to gather data for the project. This broadband challenge was only resolved in December 2019
- Two other factors have subsequently caused further delays to the pilot construction, one being a force majeure but the other is of direct significance to the business case and exploitation plan of the project
- The UK has suffered one of the wettest years on record, and while the construction of the mainframes of the homes is not impacting significantly by this the groundworks, foundations and EEB are. Delays at this stage then obviously have a knock-on impact on the installation of the rest of the ZCS
- Commercial factors have also generated delays.
 - The actual cost of the systems has increased slightly in part due to the reduced numbers, i.e. 26 units are more expensive per unit than 31.
 - Also, the installation time/cost has been higher than expected.
 - Finally, while for a long time, the BREXIT factor had not impacted the project, the housing market (sales) slowed considerably during 2019.
- The above factors resulted in a review by Project Etopia of the impact on their development viability and a pause while that was assessed
- ZCS systems have been commissioned; each of the five planned house types has been constructed, and data has been gathered from July 2019.
- In summary, the commercial and operational realities of a multi-unit residential development in the UK have created several incompatibilities with the nature and timescales of the project. These are significant factors to be considered in the exploitation and business plan element of the project.

5.3. Sant Cugat's pilot

The main conclusions of the Sant Cugat's pilot implementation are:

- There was a significant delay in the construction of the pilot. The commissioning and start-up phase of the installation was planned to end by February 2019 and finally ended in September 2019 (7 months of delay). The main reasons were:
 - The process required a public tender, which suffered various setbacks due to administrative issues. The delay was approximately 5 months.
 - During the excavation process to build the structural foundations of the STES, an asbestos cement pipe was found on site. This delayed the excavation works since it was then done manually, without machinery, in order not to damage the localized pipe and to keep the place safe.
 - The tank was redesigned in the construction phase, making it cylindrical rather than square because it was easier to assemble. Despite this ease of construction, the new design and its approval also caused a delay in the unwanted work.
- The incorporation of the PVT panels to the existing roof together with the new regulation in relation to the wooden structure obliged to perform an expensive reinforcement of the roof from June 2018 to November 2018. This fact caused a considerable increase in the costs that increased in pay-back.
- Data collection from the system operation was planned to start in March 2019, but because of the delays mentioned before, data is being collected since September 2019. During September and October 2019, the monitoring system was revised as some data was not being extracted as expected. For these reasons, it will not be possible to have a full year data as planned.
- The fact that the installation was commissioned in September 2019 makes it challenging to evaluate the operation and performance of the seasonal accumulation system during the monitored period. The seasonal accumulation is based on accumulating energy during the summer to consume it in winter. Due to construction delays, during the summer, virtually no energy was accumulated, so in winter, it was necessary to use the support system more than provided. In the coming winter, it is almost sure that the system will work at a higher performance since energy will accumulate throughout all the summer.
- After several design versions, and due to budgetary limitations, the pilot test is able to save 50% of the energy needed to heat the pool water. These savings represent about 16% of all thermal energy consumed by the installation. The pilot has the possibility of being expanded because there is still a roof-free surface and because it can supply energy for other uses (DHW and heating). As well, other buildings in the sports centre can receive the energy generated.
- The Sant Cugat pilot is an example of synergies than can be applied to other facilities. The sports centre building with the highest consumption had no space to build the tank, and its roof was oriented to the north; therefore, the pilot could not have been carried out if a solution was not found. In this case, it was to use two annexed

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buildings of the sports centre, with a very low consumption but with available space for the tank and with a south-facing roof. Although these two buildings do not receive any compensation for the use of these spaces, if the pilot test is extended it could also supply energy to these two buildings, thus creating an interest group where everyone wins.

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6. Appendix

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